

Coloured Glass Bathroom Splashbacks - Bathroom Sink Splashbacks

Fed up with trying to clean grout and mould? Use glass behind your sink, bath, in your shower enclosure and around your bathroom walls. Toughened Glass is extremely durable and easy to keep clean. It also provides a huge range of bespoke colours and designs.

We also have a wide range of vibrant and subtle colour bathroom splashbacks as well as bespoke printed images of your choice and many other premium designer finishes. A Glass Bathroom Splashback will brighten up your home and make the bathroom maintenance easy.

Bathroom Splashbacks for the SINK AREAS

Sink splashbacks are practical in any area of your home. Surround your bathroom sink with a unique, modern, and easy to clean glass bathroom sink splashback. Toothpaste stains are a thing of the past. Our glass bathroom sink splashbacks are water and heat resistant.

Bathroom Splashbacks for BATH AREAS

Our bathroom glass splashbacks are both heat and water resistant. Surround your bath with a modern, unique and easy to clean glass splashback. Cut-outs for taps and handles makes the look seamless and we can place glass within the window reveals.

Bathroom Splashbacks for SHOWER ENCLOSURES

Avoid difficult to clean grout and tiles with a modern and easy to clean surface. Customise your glass with any of our bathroom splashback finishes. Showers enclosures can be transformed with a bespoke glass splashback. Cut-outs can be made to accommodate any brackets & plumbing fittings.

AVAILABLE NOW!

We are proud to offer a new effect for all our metallic splashbacks!! The Water Droplet effect looks fantastic on our metallic splashback colours including Bronze, Silver and Rose Gold, and would make a fabulous centrepiece in any Kitchen or Bathroom. Contact us for more information.

Coloured glass is often used as an alternative to tiles. Glass splashbacks require no grouting, which means no more unsightly discoloured grout, and are easy to clean, creating a sleek modern look. It is easy to fit by securely bonding to the wall with special adhesive.

Typically glass splashbacks are manufactured in 6mm toughened safety glass; it is therefore resistant to heat and impact, whereas work surfaces are produced in 19mm toughened safety glass. Cut outs can be produced for plug

sockets, switches, hobs, sinks and basins and all splashbacks and work tops are finished with polished edges.

We use a low-iron glass, either Pilkington Optiwhite or Diamant from Saint-Gobain, as this is more optically clear than normal glass. It provides a clearer definition of the colour chosen, as normal clear glass has an inherent green characteristic which becomes more pronounced the thicker the glass. This is particularly important if splashbacks need to match the thicker work surfaces in a kitchen for example. Both thicknesses of glass have a different iron content if using normal clear glass, so the 19mm will appear greener, in turn affecting the paint colour. This issue is drastically reduced when using low-iron glass, rendering both thicknesses almost the same colour when painted.

All glass splashbacks and worktops are manufactured to order. The colour [**kitchen splashback colours**](#)

is spray painted onto the back of the glass, with a paint specially made to bond to the glass, which won't peel or flake.